

Research protocol

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Clients' experiences of Internet-based psychological treatments for mental disorders: Protocol for a metasynthesis of qualitative studies

Abstract

Background: Given the rise of Internet-based treatments (IBTs) as an effective therapeutic tool for psychological disorders, it is necessary to carry out research that examines clients' experiences with this type of intervention. The qualitative methodology has been found to be useful for analyzing clients' perceptions in terms of facilitators and barriers, acceptability, and negative effects of IBTs. However, a lack of integration of these primary studies has kept the results from being applied in new research studies and in clinical practice.

Objective: The objective of the present paper is to describe the protocol for a meta-synthesis of qualitative studies exploring the experiences of clients who underwent an IBT.

Methods: Elliot and Timulak's meta-synthesis approach will be used to review and synthesize qualitative studies related to clients' experiences in terms of the barriers and facilitators they perceived when undergoing IBTs. For each search string, the different aspects included in the SPIDER (Sample, Phenomenon of Interest, Design, Evaluation, Research type) tool will be considered. Electronic databases (PubMed, PsycINFO and Web of Science) will be searched. Two independent reviewers will analyze the material in order to determine whether the eligibility criteria are fulfilled. Findings will make it possible to create a hierarchy of domains in terms of their relevance across all the primary studies. The data obtained from primary studies will be cross-analyzed by utilizing descriptive and interpretative procedures.

Results: To date, the search strategy is being conducted. It is aimed to complete the study at the end of 2018.

Conclusions: A conceptual framework of the barriers and facilitators perceived by the clients will be developed. Implications and recommendations for clinical practice, research, and training will be suggested.

Keywords: barriers, clients' experiences; facilitators; Internet-based treatment; meta-synthesis; qualitative.

Introduction

The high prevalence rates of psychological disorders are one of the main public health concerns in contemporary society [1, 2]. Although well-established, effective psychological methods exist for the treatment of numerous disorders [3], a vast

array of problems can be identified, including relapse rates [4], dropout rates [5], iatrogenic and inert treatments [6], and the well-established gap between science and practice [7, 8].

Specifically, the dissemination of evidence-based psychological treatments has been the subject of heated debate in the past decade [9]. Lack of economic resources, being located in a remote geographical setting, or enduring the social stigma of psychological disorders are some of the barriers identified that keep people from getting access to mental health treatments [10].

In this scenario, Internet-based treatments (IBTs) have emerged as a useful alternative to cope with the challenge of disseminating psychological treatments [11]. In recent years, these types of treatments have shown ample evidence of their efficacy and effectiveness for a wide range of psychological disorders and medical conditions. The most important aspect of IBTs is the possibility of improving cost-effectiveness compared to face-to-face traditional therapy [12].

The range of IBTs includes the first treatments that were computer-based but not delivered online [13, 14]. Current interventions are all online and often recognized as online therapies. Among the vast array of online therapies or IBTs available, there are important differences that must be mentioned. Some of these therapies are self-applied treatment protocols, which have the purpose of reducing therapist support as much as possible and are even sometimes unguided. Other online treatments include some degree of therapist support, which can be delivered through e-mails, text messages, phone calls, or videoconferences. Also, there are blended treatments, which are a combination of a self-applied IBT and regular contact with a therapist at different points in time during the therapeutic process. Some studies also consider videoconference to be another kind of online therapy that can be delivered through different devices, mainly computers [15, 16]. Finally, smartphone-based interventions are becoming useful tools to improve access and perhaps the effect of treatments [17, 18].

Apart from the numerous studies focused on the extent to which IBTs are a useful tool to provide people with psychological treatments, a considerable amount of research has also examined clients' experiences with these treatments. In particular, qualitative studies have been useful to analyze clients' perceptions of a wide range of domains, including facilitators and barriers [e.g., 19], acceptability [e.g., 20], non-adherence [21], dropout [22], or negative effects [e.g., 23] of IBTs. Nevertheless, the lack of integration of these primary studies has kept the results from being applied to new research studies and clinical practice in an easier and more effective way.

In recent years, several developments within qualitative research have enhanced the quality standards. Moreover, the possibility of having tools to synthesize these studies may constitute a great leap forward. Meta-synthesis makes it possible to draw conclusions stemming from a wide range of primary studies that may focus on the same phenomenon but from different perspectives, using diverse qualitative methodologies, and in different contexts. Hence, meta-synthesis can contribute to knowledge construction by reaching new insights after the detailed analysis of the broad range of findings [24]. Furthermore, these studies can identify research gaps, develop new

theoretical and conceptual models, and provide evidence to further improve health interventions, in this case psychological interventions [25].

As Timulak [26] explains, there are two kinds of meta-syntheses: Those that aim to provide an assessment of the influence of a certain method on results reported in primary studies; and those that aim to increase the knowledge about a particular phenomenon. This study is framed in the latter approach.

In addition, by drawing on the subjective and interpretative nature of qualitative research and not being merely aggregative, this type of synthesis can contribute to construct more plausible understandings of reality and enhance its complexity (e.g. by highlighting differences and discrepancies) [27].

Aims of the study

The goal of this meta-synthesis is to review qualitative research exploring client's experiences with mental disorders that underwent an IBT. Furthermore, this study aims to synthesize and report such experiences enabling a deeper understanding of their experiences with the purpose of improving the design of the next generation of IBTs taking into consideration clients' preferences that constitutes one of the three legs incorporated by the American Psychological Association Presidential Task Force on Evidence-Based Practice [28]. Thus, new insights can emanate from such endeavor.

Methods

This meta-synthesis was registered with the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO, <http://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPERO>, registration number: CRD42018079894). The protocol was written according to the Enhancing Transparency in Reporting the Synthesis of Qualitative Research (ENTREQ statement) [27]. Instead of using the PICO (Population, Intervention, Control and Outcomes) criteria, we included the SPIDER (Sample, Phenomenon of Interest, Design, Evaluation, Research type) tool, which was specially developed for the synthesis of qualitative evidence [29].

Criteria for Study Inclusion

All the primary qualitative studies examining clients' experiences (e.g., facilitators or barriers) of an IBT for adults (18 to 65 years) with a mental disorder will be considered. By mental disorder are considered all disorders comprehended by the principal manuals of diagnosis like Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorder 4th [30] or 5th edition (DSM 5) [31] or the International Classification of Diseases 10th edition (ICD-10) [32]. Medical conditions that are not related to a mental disorder will be excluded. To be included, a study needs to present a qualitative analysis following established methodological criteria (e.g., descriptive and interpretative approach), and the data should be based on the reports (e.g., interviews, focus groups) of the participants who underwent an IBT. In the case of mixed methods, qualitative results will only be considered if they can be clearly separated from the quantitative data. Studies of completers and non-completers will be considered, including all periods of follow-up. Additionally, eligible articles will be published in English and Spanish. There will be no restriction in the search period. As aforementioned, all interventions delivered through web platforms or smartphone-based interventions are considered as IBTs, regardless the theoretical framework that the IBT is based on. This means that smartphone-based interventions (e.g. Ecological Momentary Interventions) will also be considered.

Regarding the exclusion criteria, studies that do not follow qualitative data collection methods or do not use IBT as the intervention tool will not be included. Following Timulak’s recommendations [26] for enhancing quality control, only published data will be considered. Hence, conference abstracts, unpublished manuscripts, or thesis dissertations will not be included. Moreover, studies that are not published in peer-reviewed journals will also be excluded from eligibility.

Search Strategy

All articles will be identified through the following databases: PubMed, PsycINFO, and Web of Science. For each search string, the different aspects included in the SPIDER tool will be considered. In addition, back-tracking of references from relevant articles will also be searched for additional studies. We will also identify unpublished literature through Google searches with the same keywords, and by contacting experts identified in the search of published literature.

Table 1 shows the SPIDER search strategy (see Appendix for the PUBMED search strategy).

	Description	Examples of Search Terms
Sample	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clients aged between 18 to 65 years. - Clients with diagnosis of mental disorder by the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM) or International Classification of Diseases (ICD) undergoing IBT’s. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “adult” OR “client” OR “user” OR “patient”. - “mental disorder” OR “psychological disorder”.
Phenomenon of interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clients’ experiences or perceptions of a vast array of domains undergoing an IBT. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “facilitators” OR “barriers” OR “acceptability” OR “adherence” OR “dropout” OR “negative effects”. - “Internet” OR “Internet based treatments” OR “online treatments” OR “Internet interventions” OR “e-therapy” OR “web based” OR “self-applied” OR “blended” OR “computer-based” OR “smartphone based intervention”.
Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Studies that allow the extraction of qualitative data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Interviews” OR “focus groups” OR “questionnaire” OR “survey” OR “e-mail”.

Evaluation	- Experiences, perspectives, insights, motivations or views of participants undergoing an IBT (outcome measures).	- “experience OR “view” OR “opinion” OR “attitude” OR “perception” OR “belie*” OR “belief” OR “feeling”.
	v	
Research type	- Qualitative studies or mixed methods studies.	- “qualitative” OR “mixed method”.

Selection of Studies

Two reviewers will complete all database searches, and the results obtained will be entered into Mendeley folders. All duplicates will be removed. Later, one reviewer will screen all the studies to discard the irrelevant studies that may have been subject to inclusion. Next, two independent reviewers will screen all the remaining titles and abstracts to identify potentially relevant articles and then review full texts of the relevant articles to determine eligibility. A third reviewer will resolve any discrepancies.

Quality Assessment

For the studies included, two independent reviewers will conduct an assessment according to the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) checklist for qualitative research. This checklist allows qualitative research evidence to be appraised systematically, guiding the reviewer about the results, their validity, and their transferability [33]. Two independent reviewers will screen the final selection of primary studies and a third senior reviewer (last author of this study) will resolve any discrepancies.

Data Extraction

All reviewers of the research team independently will extract data for each study using an Excel spreadsheet template to include the fundamental information such as author, year, aim of the study, number of participants, gender, setting or qualitative technique used. The whole study will be considered for the analysis, although results and discussion sections will be definitely the main parts for the data extraction given that in those sections the core data obtained by each study is described.

Data Analysis

Following the Elliott and Timulak guidelines [34], a descriptive and interpretative approach will be considered. This method makes it possible to include a more phenomenological perspective by carrying out a detailed description of the primary studies, and complement it with a hermeneutical perspective that goes beyond the given information and, therefore, reaches new conclusions. Specifically, this approach includes four stages in which the data analysis process is carried out. First, the collected data are ordered in domains, which represent high order conceptualizations of the phenomenon. Second, meaning units are outlined that represent the smallest piece of information from the data with an understandable meaning. Domains provide a conceptual and flexible framework for the data and can be modified by the researcher

until they fit the data. Third, the meaning units are organized in categories and classified in the existing domains. The creation of categories is an interpretative process performed by the researcher, who would try to respect the data and use category labels close to the original language provided by the participants [35]. If there are similarities between the established categories, second-order categories could be organized. Finally, the results are abstracted in different forms, such as figures or narratives to better grasp the phenomena. Following the recommendations by Levitt, Motulosky, Wertz, Morrow and Ponterotto [36], methodological integrity (in terms of fidelity and utility) will be pursued. Thus, the different considerations at both the data collection and data analysis levels will be fulfilled. All the researchers involved in the analytic process will have extensive experience in the use of technologies to deliver psychological treatments. Figure 1 shows the data analysis process that will be conducted. In total, 5 researchers (authors 1 to 5) will be in charge of the data analysis. Each researcher will develop a domain structure which finally will be discussed in an iterative process until a consensus among all the alternatives is met. For the delineation of meaning units, the final number of primary studies will be divided among the coders but still ensuring that every study will be coded by two researchers in order to guarantee methodological rigor. For this second step, an iterative process will also be conducted to reach a consensus. Additionally, through this iterative process, categories that capture the fundamental sense of the meaning units are elaborated [26].

(Figure 1)

Discussion

Although there has been an abundance of qualitative studies in recent years, there is a lack of studies designed to synthesize the results. This synthesis is an essential step in outlining more general conclusions about the experiences of clients undergoing IBTs. As long as available IBTs do not differ much (at least in some general features), the overall experiences can be consistently integrated. In particular, qualitative studies have focused on studying topics such as facilitators, barriers, acceptability, adherence, dropouts, and negative effects. This meta-synthesis will more accurately weigh the extent to which the different topics related to clients' experiences have been addressed, in addition to establishing a taxonomy within each of these topics in order to foster its use in new research studies and in the clinical application of IBTs.

Findings will make it possible to create a hierarchy of domains in terms of their relevance across all the primary studies. In this regard, a conceptual framework of the barriers and facilitators perceived by the clients will be developed. Implications and recommendations for clinical practice, research, and training will be suggested.

Potential Sources of Limitations

First and foremost, as in any other kind of review, the findings will depend on the quality of the primary studies included. Although there will be a particular emphasis on assessing the quality of the primary studies, it is a difficult task to accurately assess these kinds of studies. Moreover, there may be relevant studies in other languages that will not be included because only English and Spanish articles will be considered.

Furthermore, meta-synthesis is a powerful tool in order to draw overall conclusion from a certain topic. However, it may be subject to potential under-representation of richness of primary studies given that the material of analysis is not the raw data of each included study.

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Conflict of Interest

None declared.

Abbreviations:

CASP: Critical Appraisal Skills Program.

ENTREQ: Enhancing Transparency in Reporting the Synthesis of Qualitative Research.

IBT'S: Internet Based Treatments.

PICO: Population, Intervention, Control and Outcomes.

PROSPERO: International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews.

SPIDER: Sample, Phenomenon of Interest, Design, Evaluation, Research type.

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